

Closing the gap: a spatially targeted approach to water point rehabilitation in Tanzania

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Summary

WHO/UNICEF estimate 387 million people lack access to drinking water in Sub-Saharan Africa. This is the only global region where the gap is growing, being hampered by sustained non-functionality of water infrastructure. In 2015, 29% of water points in Tanzania were non-functional. This work updates functionality estimates and uses a novel combination of global satellite data with government water point data to estimate rural population water access at a 1km resolution. The results show higher water access (58.8%) compared to UNICEF/WHO estimates and identify non-functioning water points that will lead to the most substantial increase in population access.

KEYWORDS: water point accessibility, big satellite data, PostGIS, data-driven decision making, Tanzania

1 Water access in Tanzania

Access to water and sanitation are recognised as a human right by the United Nations, yet in 2023 703 million people still lack access to basic drinking water services (WHO, 2023). Sub-Saharan Africa is the only region in the world where the number of people without access to improved water (protected from contamination) is growing. According to WHO and UNICEF about 387 million people lacked access in 2020, rising from 250 million in 2000. Such access is pivotal in combating water borne diseases such as under nutrition and stunting in children (Sahiledengle et al., 2022),

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diarrheal disease (Merid et al., 2023), cholera (Ayling et al., 2023; Gething et al., 2023), typhoid (Kim et al., 2023), and infestation with intestinal parasites (e.g. geohelminths) (Moraes & Cairncross, 2004). Further, the water and sanitation crisis creates an estimated global economic loss of US\$260 billion in developing countries whilst installing appropriate infrastructure and water facilities would generate a 21 times return on the initial outlay (Hutton, 2013; Joseph et al., 2019; WaterAid, 2021).

Despite this, installation of new infrastructure alone cannot be the solution. Water point and water schemes failures have been documented in studies across many African countries including Tanzania (Joseph et al., 2019), Ghana (Marks et al., 2014), Nigeria (Andres et al., 2018), Mozambique (Jansz, Shamila, 2011). In Tanzania, Joseph et al. (2019) reported that 29% of water points were not functional in 2015, whilst 20% of new water points were failing within the first year (Joseph et al., 2018; Komakech et al., 2020; Lemmens et al., 2017).

In order to track and better address the issues around water point functionality, the Government of Tanzania has engaged in large-scale efforts to map rural water points since 2002, started by the Tanzanian Water Department in conjunction with WaterAid (Taylor, 2014). These have continued to the present day under what is now the Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Agency (RUWASA) within the Ministry of Water. This agency houses the Rural Service Delivery and Management System (RSDMS) where a core focus is to consolidate and use available rural water point data for better policy and planning, supported by the World Bank Program for Results (PforR) investment *Sustainable Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Program (SRWSSP)*. SRWSSP supports the Government of Tanzania's Water Sector Development Program (WSDP) in expanding access to improved water supply and sanitation services in rural areas. The investment of this project is a total of \$650 million, and by 2022 (after three years of the program), it is estimated that 3.3 million people had already gained access to improved water supply.

Given that the investment is output-based in design, there is a strong motivation to improve population water accessibility data. Until now the Ministry assumed each rural water point served a maximum of 250 users, with population estimated from the census or with community consultations. Though the Water Point Mapping System initiatives have geo-located and determined water point functionality, they are still yet to find a more accurate method of appropriately reflecting population coverage across the country (Lemmens et al., 2017).

As such, whilst functionality is monitored, repairs are not presently being prioritized based on population served. This work therefore presents a spatial assessment of population served through a unique combination of *big grided satellite data* including population density, accessibility, land cover and water point functionality to estimate rural population served at a 1km resolution across Tanzania. Outputs will enable the first data-informed allocation of new water points and repairs, assisting the Ministry of Water in optimizing investments to maximise rural water accessibility, and make significant steps to attaining national and international targets. The methodology is fully reproducible enabling future replication with new or updated water point data.

2 Spatial data solution

2.1 Overview

Our approach outputs 1.1 million 1km cells covering the entirety of Tanzania considering accessibility based on *walking time* to 105,000 water points. Each cell contains data on population, time to water point and land cover. Combing this with Local Government Area data we have computed the rural population that have access to safe drinking water within 30 minutes, enabling direct comparison with the progress on household drinking water report produced by UNICEF and the WHO (2023).

Data sets used within the analysis (Table 1) are openly available with the exclusion of the water point locations (provided by RUWASA) and administrative boundaries (provided by the President’s Office, Regional Administration and Local Government (PO-RALG), Government of Tanzania). These could be replaced with open data from the [water point data exchange](#) (WPDX) and [the Database of Global Administrative Areas](#) (GADM) boundaries respectively. The code developed in this work is hosted on GitHub: https://github.com/spet2094/Tz_P4

Table 1: Input data for calculating rural water point accessibility at 1km cells for Tanzania.

Data set	Characteristics	Source	Purpose
Water point location and functionality	105,000 points	World Bank Central Data Management Team (CDMT), 2019	Compute access to each point
Population count	Population count at 100m resolution	WorldPop , 2020	Compute the number of people accessing each water point
Friction surface	Walking-only friction surface (time to cross a cell) at 1km resolution.	Malaria Atlas Project , 2020	Generate accessibility raster
Land cover	1km land cover tiles	European Union Global Human Settlement Layer , 2020	Remove urban areas from the analysis
Administrative boundaries	184 Local Government Authority Areas (LGAs)	Development Impact Evaluation Unit (DIME), World Bank, originally from the Government of Tanzania	Aggregate results to LGAs (e.g. districts and regions)

2.2 Methodology

The presented analysis was conducted in a combination of R and PostGIS, being divided into three work packages (Figure 1): (1) accessibility to the nearest water point per 1km cell, (2) cell based analysis, computing population, accessibility and land cover per 1km cell and (3) Local Government Authority analysis calculating the population within 30 minutes of a water point. At the time of devising the methodology PostGIS was selected due to the volume of data and the geometry extension. However, the spatial extension in DuckDB now presents an alternative solution.

This methodology was replicated for two instances (a) functioning and (b) all water points (including non-functioning), with a PostGIS processing time of around 10 minutes per instance. A *brief* summary of each work package is provided:

2.2.1 (1) accessibility to the nearest water point

The friction surface (developed by Malaria Atlas project) contains a nominal overall speed of walking to travel across each cell derived from Open Street Map (OSM) and Google (Weiss et al., 2020). Taking this data, Queen's case contiguity transition costs were computed, followed by an accumulated cost surface through the least-cost distance from origin points (each individual friction cell) to destination water points using Dijkstra's algorithm implemented in the `gdistance` R package (Etten, 2017). This returns a value of time in minutes to the nearest water point per 1km cell.

2.2.2 (2) cell based analysis

Work package 2 dealt with combining datasets of different spatial resolutions. The 1km accessibility output from (1) was used as a base layer to join World Pop population estimates (100m) and Global Human Settlement land cover (1km) data, both with different spatial extents. For population data, the 100m cells were converted to points, intersected and summed with the 1km accessibility grid.

The Global Human Settlement land cover was used to remove urban areas from the rural water point calculation. To account for the different extents the 1km accessibility data was converted to point and used to query (and extract) the land cover per 1km cell. This output was re-joined with original 1km grid, giving population, accessibility and land cover for each 1km cell. Finally, a dummy column was created based on the 30 minute accessibility threshold.

2.2.3 (3) Local Government Authority analysis

To prioritize areas for investment and aid visualisation results were aggregated to district areas, giving the percent of the population in each district within 30 minutes of a water point. This was achieved through a spatial join, where 1km cells that overlapped multiple LGA boundaries were assigned to the LGA with the largest overlap. However, in PostGIS no such argument exists (e.g. `st_join(x,y, join=st_intersects, largest=TRUE)`) and so was computed through a series of intersects and joins.

The analysis of the data has been completed and we have recently commenced interpretations.

Figure 1: Methodology for (1) wrangling inputs (top), (2) determining population, accessibility and land cover for 1km cells across Tanzania (middle) and (3) summary statistics for Local Government Areas (bottom).

3 Implications of the work

From the rural population of 42 million (as determined by Global Human Settlement land cover) 58.81% (24.7 million) have access to a functioning water point within 30 minutes, while 71.76% (30.16 million) have access to *any* water point within 30 minutes. Whilst our results show that Tanzania is ahead of the the 2022 UNICEF/WHO estimate of 49% (UNICEF & WHO, 2023), accessibility varies substantially across the 31 regions (Figure 2) and 184 districts (Figure 3 and Table 2).

When dis-aggregating by districts this ranges from 7.33% to a functioning water point in Ulanaga to almost complete access in Shia (96.82%) and Hai (97.63%). From this analysis we can identify districts that would provide the greatest *current* return on investment. In the district of Geita 31.19% of the population have access to a functioning water point yet 47.88% have access to any water point. If all water points in Geita were repaired it would yield the largest population increase in water accessibility for all districts in Tanzania, with an additional 314,889 people being able to access water (Table 2).

Table 2: Top 5 districts that would provide the greatest return on investment in terms of population accessibility if all non-functioning water points were repaired.

District	% population access to functioning water point	% population access to any water point	Population increase if all non-functional points repaired
Geita	31.19	61.35	314,889
Rorya	21.30	75.16	140,454
Ulanga	7.34	71.96	134,662
Tandahimba	45.29	90.68	118,314
Kigoma	54.39	89.96	117,951

It is evident that Tanzania does have the existing infrastructure to meet their first WSDP target of 69% of rural water coverage by 2010 (The United Republic of Tanzania, 2002). From the 184 districts, fixing all water points in the top 61 districts (based on number of people who have a non-functional water point in 30 minutes) would return access to an additional 4.29 million people, 69% of the rural population. Nevertheless, even if all non-functioning water points were restored this would only return access to an additional 5.4 million (71.79%) indicating that additional investment will be required to attain the WSDP target of 90% by 2025 and Sustainable Goal 6 of universal access by 2030. This approach does not account for future population growth, however, ongoing work will consider annual population growth rates between 2000-2020 and attempt to predict future water demand, assuming the same growth trajectory. Given new or updated population or water point data the analysis could easily be re-computed.

Whilst this provides an example of optimising financial investment it does not address population growth, the financial cost of rehabilitation and new infrastructure or equity in water point accessi-

Figure 2: Percent of rural population with access to a functional water point and any water point (including non-functional water points) per region.

Figure 3: Accessibility of all 1km cells to (A) a functional water point and (B) any water point (including non-functional water points) whilst (C) shows the percent of the rural population with access to a functional water point at the district level.

bility, the latter being another component of Sustainable Goal 6 (Zhai et al., 2023). It is essential that target-based funding is adaptable to the changing accessibility requirements of the population. As such, Tanzania faces the challenging prospect of managing competing interests from national and international goals.

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Biographies

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Sophie Ayling is a PhD Researcher at the Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), University College London and a Data Specialist Consultant for the World Bank. Her research and professional engagements are focused on employing data, especially spatial data to inform water & sanitation, urban development and health policy and planning in developing countries.

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